

FUEL CONSUMPTION AND CO₂ EMISSION FORECAST ON DIVERGING DIAMOND INTERCHANGE

ALEKSANDAR JOVANOVIĆ¹, KATARINA KUKIĆ², ANA UZELAC³

¹ Faculty of Engineering University of Kragujevac, Kragujevac, a.jovanovic@kg.ac.rs, 0000-0003-4208-5703

² University of Belgrade, Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, Belgrade, k.kukic@sf.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0001-7369-2456

³ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, Belgrade, ana.uzelac@sf.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0002-7203-9567

Abstract: *Traffic-related pollution continues to pose serious challenges to both environmental sustainability and public health. Road transportation is a major contributor, accounting for approximately 14% of global greenhouse gas emissions. This study focuses on predicting fuel consumption and emissions at Diamond Diverge Interchanges (DDIs), based on traffic demand. Accounting for the significant impact of heavy vehicle stops on overall emissions, the study introduces a novel ecological performance metric specifically designed for DDIs. Subsequently, six machine learning models are applied to predict fuel use and emissions, with the Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) model achieving the best performance for CO₂ prediction (MAE = 620.78, R² = 0.9989), followed closely by the Artificial Neural Network (ANN). In contrast, the Ensemble Trees model showed the weakest performance, with the highest prediction errors and the lowest R² value (0.9423).*

Keywords: *DDI, emissions, Bee Colony Optimization, microsimulation, machine learning.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Air pollution originating from road traffic is a major contributor to environmental harm and poses serious risks to human health. The transportation sector is responsible for nearly 14% of greenhouse gas emissions worldwide. Beyond CO₂ and fuel use, it also emits harmful substances such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), and hydrocarbons (HC), which are linked to respiratory and heart-related conditions. As both vehicle numbers and travel demands grow, the environmental consequences are expected to worsen (IEA, 2019; WHO, 2019). To mitigate these issues, transportation professionals are increasingly turning to innovative intersection and interchange designs.

One such design is the Diverging Diamond Interchange (DDI), which enhances traffic operations and safety and has the potential to lower emissions and fuel use (Hughes et al., 2014). However, DDIs generally require more physical space than conventional intersections, limiting their use in densely populated urban centers. As a result, they are more often constructed in suburban areas, where there is more available land and where urban and rural traffic streams intersect. In most implementations, DDIs are controlled using fixed-time signals with two main phases. This is primarily due to the straightforward nature of such phasing, where each phase serves traffic either on the bridge or from the ramps. Although more complex phasing schemes with overlapping movements have been proposed, they have not yet been adopted in practice (Schroeder et al., 2014).

This study focuses on predicting fuel use and emissions, specifically CO₂ at DDIs with the goal to estimate environmental impact based solely on traffic intensity at different entry points of the DDI. For the purpose of this research, cycle lengths and phase splits are optimized using Bee Colony Optimization (BCO), a nature-inspired algorithm (Lučić & Teodorović, 2001). This technique has shown promise in prior applications involving alternative intersection control strategies (Jovanović & Teodorović, 2022). After optimization, simulations are conducted to record fuel consumption and emissions, forming the dataset used to train and test machine learning (ML) models. Findings highlight that the frequency of stops for heavy vehicles plays a crucial role in determining both fuel usage and emission levels. This observation offers a new angle compared to the older Robertson performance index (Robertson et al., 1980), which has been a long-standing metric in signal control evaluation. In this work, the ecological performance measure introduced by Alshayeb, Stevanovic, and Effinger (2022) is adopted as a more suitable alternative.

Machine learning has so far shown to be successful at predicting CO₂ emissions in different transport-related contexts. For example, Udoh et al. (2024) applied ML techniques to estimate emissions from light-duty vehicles using data from the UK Vehicle Certification Agency. Among six regression models tested, the

Decision Tree Regressor achieved the highest accuracy, with engine power, fuel consumption, and engine capacity identified as key predictors. The final model was deployed as a Streamlit-based web application, providing a practical tool for estimating emissions and supporting sustainable transport decisions. Park et al. (2023) created a model including traffic volume, speed, and wind data to forecast urban on-road CO₂ levels in Seoul. Their findings revealed significant differences in emissions across locations and times of day, demonstrating the model's utility in urban monitoring and policy planning. Using data from portable emissions measurement systems, Li et al. (2024) suggested a deep learning technique to forecast CO₂ emissions from light-duty diesel trucks. They identified key predictors such as vehicle speed, acceleration, road slope, and vehicle-specific power and created a model with good accuracy.

2. METHODOLOGY

To develop predictive models for fuel consumption and emissions at a Diverging Diamond Interchange (DDI), we first generated a comprehensive dataset using a simulation-based approach. A wide variety of traffic demand patterns were defined, covering both bridge and ramp volumes, including the proportion of heavy goods vehicles (HGVs). The methodology may be divided into subtasks, as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The methodology divided into three subtasks

Subtask 1: The goal of the fixed-time optimization at a DDI is to determine the best values for cycle length (C) and green times (g_j) that minimize the Ecological Performance Index (EPI). The optimization is subject to constraints on total cycle time ($C_{min} \leq C \leq C_{max}$), green time ranges per phase ($g_{jmin} \leq g_j \leq g_{jmax}$), and the requirement that green times and lost time together sum up to the cycle length ($\sum_{j=1}^2 g_j = C - L$), where L is the cycle lost time, consisting of both yellow time and all-red time, each set to 3 seconds per phase. In this case, L takes the value of 12 seconds. The EPI is computed for each lane based on vehicle delay, number of stops, and a stop penalty factor, as defined by (1):

$$EPI_i = d_i + K_i \cdot S_i \quad (1)$$

where d_i is the average delay (s/veh), S_i is the average number of stops (stops/veh), and K_i is the stop penalty (Alshayeb, Stevanovic and Effinger, 2022). The total EPI for the intersection is a demand-weighted sum across all lanes (totally i traffic lanes) over the sum of traffic demands q_i at the i -th lane, and is calculated as in (2):

$$EPI = \frac{\sum_i q_i \cdot EPI_i}{\sum_i q_i} \quad (2)$$

The BCO algorithm was applied in this approach, with a population of agents (bees) iteratively searching for better signal settings, starting from feasible initial solutions and improving them through several iterations. The setup used in this study included 20 bees, 20 forward-backwards passes, one solution change per pass and a stopping condition based on CPU time of 10 seconds. At the start of the search, an initial solution is randomly generated from the feasible solution space.

Subtask 2: The modelled DDI is based on a real-world layout from Lincoln, Nebraska (USA), Figure 2 and was implemented in the VISSIM simulation environment. Simulations were run for one hour with a 150-second warm-up period, using 42 random seeds. The speed limit was set to 72 km/h, and the bridge length was 105 meters. A standard two-phase DDI signal plan was applied.

During simulations, vehicle behavior (including speed, position, acceleration, deceleration, and road slope) was recorded every second and stored in “fzp” files. These files were then processed using the Comprehensive Modal Emissions Model (CMEM) to estimate fuel use and emissions. This procedure was repeated for all traffic demand patterns, resulting in a dataset of 252 entries, where inputs are traffic demands and outputs are fuel consumption and emissions.

Subtask 3: The dataset was split into an 80/20 ratio to obtain 200 samples for ML models training and 50 for testing. To simplify inputs, traffic demands were grouped into bridge (A and E on Figure 2) and highway (B and F) flows. Additionally, the percentage of heavy vehicles was considered for both sources, given its strong influence on emissions, since one of the main components that influences the ecological parameters is the number of stops of heavy vehicles (Alshayeb, Stevanovic, and Effinger, 2022). As a result, four input features were defined: X_1 – traffic demands from the highway, X_2 – the percentage of heavy vehicles from the highway, X_3 – traffic demands on the bridge and X_4 – the percentage of heavy vehicles on the bridge. The Vissim & CMEM model then provided five outputs: fuel consumption (FC), carbon dioxide (CO₂), hydrocarbons (HC), carbon monoxide (CO), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). This approach enabled the creation of dataset that will be used within predictive ML models capable of learning from traffic patterns and estimating environmental impacts.

Figure 2: DDI layout

To predict fuel consumption (FC) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, this study applies a set of regression models, including both traditional and advanced approaches, chosen for their strong performance in multivariable prediction tasks. Specifically, the following regression models were considered: Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Random Forest Regression (RFR), Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), Ensemble Trees (Boosted Regression) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) with a single hidden layer. Two sets of models were developed with input variables X_1 , X_2 , X_3 and X_4 , and the output in one set of models is FC, and in the other set is CO₂.

In order to evaluate regression models, we used four commonly employed metrics: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Coefficient of Determination (R^2), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). MAE represents the average of the absolute differences between the predicted and actual values. It provides a straightforward interpretation of the average magnitude of prediction errors, without considering their direction. MAE is less sensitive to outliers, and it is calculated by formula (3):

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (3)$$

where n is the number of instances in the test dataset, y_i is the actual value of output for the i th data point, and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value of output by the model for the i th data point.

RMSE is the square root of the average of squared differences between predicted and observed values. Because it squares the errors before averaging, RMSE penalizes larger errors more strongly than MAE, making it useful when large deviations are particularly undesirable. It is calculated by formula (4):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (4)$$

R^2 , or the coefficient of determination, indicates the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variables. It ranges from 0 to 1, where with higher value the model explains more of the variability in the response variable. It is obtained as in (5), where \bar{y}_i is mean of all observed values:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2} \quad (5)$$

Finally, MAPE expresses the average absolute error as a percentage of actual values, making it useful for understanding model accuracy in relative terms. However, it should be used with caution when actual values are close to zero, as this can result in very high or undefined percentage errors. It is calculated by formula (6):

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{|y_i|} \quad (6)$$

Before presenting the obtained results, we will briefly explain several regression models applied in this study. The MLR model served as a baseline due to its simplicity and interpretability. It assumes a linear relationship between inputs and the target variable, making it easy to implement but limited in capturing complex, nonlinear patterns. The SVR model uses a kernel function to project data into a higher-dimensional space where a linear fit can approximate nonlinear relationships (Support Vector Machines algorithm for regression problems). Random Forest and Ensemble Trees (Boosting) are representatives of ensemble learning techniques. RFR builds multiple decision trees using bootstrap samples and averages their predictions, reducing variance and improving generalization. In contrast, Boosted Regression builds trees sequentially, where each new tree attempts to correct the errors of the previous one. This often leads to improved accuracy but requires careful tuning to avoid overfitting. GPR is a probabilistic, non-parametric model that assumes a distribution over functions and provides both predictions and uncertainty estimates. It is a Bayesian approach that can model certainty in predictions, especially effective in small to medium datasets and is valued for its flexibility and ability to model uncertainty explicitly, though computational cost can grow significantly with larger datasets. Lastly, ANNs are a class of ML models inspired by the structure and function of the human brain. ANNs consist of interconnected nodes (neurons) arranged in layers that process input data and make predictions. It is highly effective at capturing complex nonlinear relationships in the data. While neural networks require more data and computational resources, they offer strong predictive performance when properly trained and regularized.

3. RESULTS

All applied models were trained using default parameters provided by MATLAB’s Regression Learner and Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox. All models were trained and tested using an 80/20 split of the dataset. To ensure fair comparison, 10-fold cross-validation was performed, meaning that the given data sample is to be split into 10 groups. Recall briefly that k-fold cross-validation estimates model performance on unseen data using a k-subset of the data. It provides a more realistic evaluation than methods like a basic train/test split. This process evaluates the model design by retraining it with different data subsets. The steps are: 1. shuffle the dataset and split it into k parts (10 in this study); 2. for each part, use it as a test set and the remaining parts as a training set; 3. train the model, evaluate it, and save the score; 4. the final results represent average performance across folds, providing a more robust insight into generalization performance.

We developed six ML regression models with the following parameters:

- LMR (with `fitlm` MATLAB function): a simple, interpretable model that serves as a baseline model
- SVR (with `fitrsvm` MATLAB function): Kernel: 'linear' showed better results than 'gaussian', other parameters set to default values (BoxConstraint (C): 1, Epsilon: 0.1, Standardization: Enabled)
- RFR (with `fitrensemble` MATLAB function): Method: Bagging, 100 learning trees, Learner type: Regression trees with default depth
- Boosted Trees (with `fitrensemble` MATLAB function): Method: Least-squares boosting, 100 learning trees, Learner rate: 0.1, Trees are grown sequentially with focus on correcting previous errors
- GPR (with `fitrgp` MATLAB function): Kernel function: Squared Exponential, Basis function: Constant, Noise standard deviation and kernel parameters are estimated from the data
- ANN (with `fitnet` MATLAB function): Architecture: Feedforward NN, Hidden layer: 1 layer with 10 neurons, Training function: Levenberg–Marquardt (default function for small-to-medium datasets).

In Table 1, we present an evaluation of applied regression models for the prediction of CO₂ emissions, with the following performance metrics: MAE, RMSE, MAPE and R².

Table 1: Evaluation of performed regression models for the prediction of CO₂ emissions

Model	MAE	RMSE	MAPE	R ²
MLR	1618.3	2280.6	1.0736	0.99774
SVR	3542.9	4382.2	2.2076	0.99104
RFR	6110.1	9344.5	4.1557	0.95825
Ensemble Trees	8417.4	11109	5.2746	0.94233
GPR	620.78	1339.9	0.36664	0.9989
ANN	750.2	1432.7	0.45287	0.99886

Table 1 summarizes the predictive performance of six regression models. Among them, Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) achieved the best overall results, indicating excellent accuracy and model fit. Note that Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) also demonstrated strong performance, with the additional benefit of model interpretability through explicit coefficients, confidence intervals, and significance testing. So, we will briefly

present MLR in more detail and interpret the obtained results. Table 2 presents estimated coefficients and interpretation of the MLR Model described by the equation:

$$CO_2\text{emission} = -53735 + 197.2 \cdot X_1 + 13264 \cdot X_2 + 97.3 \cdot X_3 + 12685 \cdot X_4 + \varepsilon \quad (7)$$

Table 2: Estimated coefficients and interpretation of the MLR model for prediction of CO2 emissions

Input	Coefficient	t-stat	p-value	Interpretation
Intercept	-53735	-60.8	≈ 0	Baseline emission level (has no practical meaning by itself — as it is unrealistic for all inputs to be zero).
X ₁	197.2	25.2	<0.001	An increase in highway traffic demand by 1 unit increases CO ₂ emissions by 197.2 g, assuming all other factors remain constant.
X ₂	13264	17.6	<0.001	Each additional percentage of heavy vehicles from the highway increase leads to a 13.26 kg rise in CO ₂ emissions.
X ₃	97.3	11.9	<0.001	An increase in traffic demand on the bridge by 1 unit results in a 97.3 g increase in CO ₂ emissions.
X ₄	12685	15.9	<0.001	Each additional percentage of heavy vehicles from the bridge increases emissions by approximately 12.7 kg.

From the presented results, we conclude that the MLR model shows excellent performance and interpretability, with an R² of 0.998. Among the predictors, the percentage of heavy vehicles from the highway and from the bridge has the largest impact on CO₂ emissions. This result is expected, as a higher share of freight vehicles significantly increases fuel consumption and emissions.

In the same way, we developed another six ML regression models for the prediction of fuel consumption (FC) in dependence of the same four input variables. The obtained performances are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Evaluation of performed regression models for the prediction of fuel consumption (FC)

Model	MAE	RMSE	MAPE	R ²
MLR	2858.4	3507.5	5.0792	0.95264
SVR	2824.9	3642.2	5.1302	0.93983
RFR	1998.1	3069.9	3.2852	0.95806
Ensemble Trees	2596.4	3621.6	4.2552	0.94282
GPR	309.6	477.92	0.55646	0.999
ANN	242.61	382.91	0.42099	0.99936

Among the tested models, the ANN and GPR achieved the best performance, with extremely low MAE, RMSE, and MAPE values, and R² values close to 1. This indicates high predictive accuracy. In contrast, linear regression and SVR performed reasonably well but showed noticeably higher error rates. Overall, the non-linear models captured the complexity of fuel consumption data more effectively than linear approaches.

Both the Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models demonstrated outstanding accuracy in predicting fuel consumption. The ANN model achieved the highest R² value (0.99936) and the lowest error metrics overall, indicating its strong ability to capture complex nonlinear relationships. However, due to its black-box nature, it lacks interpretability, which can be a limitation in practical transportation engineering contexts.

On the other hand, the GPR model also delivered highly accurate predictions (R² = 0.999), with the added benefit of providing confidence intervals around its predictions, which enhances model transparency and reliability. This feature makes GPR particularly useful in scenarios where understanding the uncertainty in predictions is crucial.

Figure 3 presents the 95% confidence intervals of the GPR model's predictions concerning input features X₁ (traffic demands on the highway) and X₃ (traffic demands from the bridge), offering visual insight into how the model's confidence varies across different traffic conditions. It illustrates the effect of individual input features (X₁ and X₃) on the predicted fuel consumption using the GPR model. For each subplot, one feature is varied across its observed range while the others are fixed at their mean values. The blue line shows the model prediction, while the shaded area represents the 95% confidence interval. These plots reveal how sensitive the fuel consumption is to each input, with X₁ (traffic demand on the highway) and X₃ (traffic demand on the bridge) both showing strong and nearly linear relationships with fuel use. The narrow confidence bands indicate high model certainty in these regions.

Figure 3: Confidence intervals of GPR predictions

4. CONCLUSION

This study advances the application of predictive modelling and optimization to tackle pressing issues related to traffic-related emissions and fuel consumption at Diamond Diverge Interchanges (DDIs). By relying solely on traffic demand patterns as input, we have developed models capable of accurately predicting CO₂ and fuel consumption. BCO is used to optimize signal control, demonstrating the promise of bio-inspired algorithms in enhancing ecological performance.

In addition, six machine learning algorithms were developed and applied to predict fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions. ANN and GPR models showed the best performances. Moreover, the MLR model demonstrated strong performance in predicting CO₂ emissions (R² of 0.998), which is why it was used for interpreting the obtained results. The model shows that all analyzed variables significantly affect CO₂ emissions ($p < 0.001$), with the percentage of heavy vehicles from the highway (X₂) being the most important variable, as it has the highest coefficient (13.26 kg per percent) and thus the strongest impact on emission increase.

Future research will be directed to applying this methodology over the whole corridor or network at classical intersections.

LITERATURE

- International Energy Agency (IEA), (2019). Global EV Outlook 2019; IEA: Paris, France.
- World Health Organization, (2019). Ambient air pollution: training for health care providers (No. WHO/CED/PHE/EPE/19.12. 14). World Health Organization.
- Hughes, W., Jagannathan, R., Sengupta, D. and Hummer, J. (2010). Alternative intersections/interchanges: informational report (AIIR) (No. FHWA-HRT-09-060). *Federal Highway Administration. Office of Research, Development, and Technology*. United States.
- Lucic, P. & Teodorovic, D. (2001). Bee system: modeling combinatorial optimization transportation engineering problems by swarm intelligence. In *Preprints of the TRISTAN IV triennial symposium on transportation analysis* (pp. 441-445).
- Jovanović, A. & Teodorović, D. (2022). Fixed-time traffic control at superstreet intersections by bee colony optimization. *Transportation research record*, 2676(4), (pp. 228-241).
- Alshayeb, S., Stevanovic, A. & Effinger, J.R. (2022). Investigating impacts of various operational conditions on fuel consumption and stop penalty at signalized intersections. *International Journal of Transportation Science and Technology*, 11(4), (pp. 690-710).
- Teodorović, D., Davidović, T., Šelmić, M. and Nikolić, M. (2021). Bee colony optimization and its applications. *Handbook of AI-based Metaheuristics*, (pp. 301-322).
- Udoh, J., Lu, J., & Xu, Q. (2024). Application of machine learning to predict CO₂ emissions in light-duty vehicles. *Sensors*, 24(24), 8219.
- Park, C., Jeong, S., Kim, C., Shin, J., & Joo, J. (2023). Machine learning-based estimation of urban on-road CO₂ concentration in Seoul. *Environmental Research*, 231, 116256.
- Li, S., Tong, Z., & Haroon, M. (2024). Estimation of transport CO₂ emissions using machine learning algorithm. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 133, 104276.